

Pre and Post Effects of Joining Self Help Groups on Involvement in Income Generating Activities, Savings Parking and Factors Driving Women Sustainability: A study W.R.T. Chikkaballapura District

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Abstract

Purpose: The main purpose of the present paper is to find how far the demographics impact on the respondents involvement in Income Generating Activities (IGAs), Status of respondents before and after joining SHGs, and drivers of women sustainability. Micro Finance offers a range of small amount financial products aiming to address market failures (Gatto, 2018). Microfinance intends to provide the poor and vulnerable categories with solutions to face the imperfection of credit, banking and insurance markets (Ray, 2008). Empirical findings reveal that microfinance through microcredit has positively improvised the wellbeing of women. It is considered as a powerful tool for uplifting the economic conditions of poor through group approach (Juja S. V. 2014).

Methodology: A well designed pre tested questionnaire was administered as schedule due to the existing level of literacy among respondents and to avoid non-response and incompleteness. Chi-square, contingency co-efficient, modified comparative ANOVA, Kendall's co-efficient of concordance, and Extent of Sustainability Index (ESI) were performed. The respondents belongs to 6 villages of 6 blocks Chikkaballapura districts.

Findings: The findings of the study includes that demographics of respondents are significantly affecting with high degree of relationship. All the profiles are highly varying with more than 0.5 contingency co-efficient. 18 respondents before joining SHGs were strongly involved in harvesting commercial crops, 16 in tailoring, 11 in masala packing. The status of respondents after joining SHGs found huge increase from 18 to 33 in working in harvesting of commercial crops and well supports that Chikkaballapura district which is famous for commercial vegetables growing and marketing and supplies vegetables to Hyderabad and Mumbai. Further, a marginal jump is found in embracing tailoring job, running petty shops, and working in grocery shop with delivery service. Similarly the study found major changes in between before and after joining of SHGs as far as savings are concerned. 24 respondents before joining parked their savings with chit funds, 22 respondents with neighbours etc., and after joining the members 53 started savings parking with SHGs. Very significantly investing savings with chit funds and relatives etc were significantly reduced and they have started saving with SHGs. The drivers of women sustainability found to be development of financial skills, and quality of leadership, secondly cooperation between the members, and thirdly using loan for productive purpose.

Keywords: Savings, productive purpose, commercial crops, mutual funds, before and after, rural development

Introduction

Previous researches reveal that microfinance is strongly attempting to eliminate unemployment, poverty and assist in the process of bringing the poor, deserved and not accessed by the formal financial institutions due to lack of collateral. The emergence of microfinance can be traced to the failure of organised financial institutions lack of contact with the poor. Innovations like group lending, joint liability, dynamic incentives, frequent repayment schedules and women

together as clients have impacted very much on microfinance and as a consequence of this trend there is a change in microfinance practices. To have a sustainable life style along with saving and investment microfinance allows the poor to avail loan that leads to the financial independence and growth (Sanjeeb Kumar Dubey, 2015)^[24]. Access to financial services has been recognised as a human right. Strengthening credit delivery services and increasing their outreach has always been an important

component of Indian government strategy (M. Hudson et al. 2020) [14]. Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) emerged as a holistic financial solutions to the poor that offers agile, flexible and low cost financial service (J.P.C. Ribeiro et al. 2022) [10]. Today most of the MFIs are hybrid in nature aiming at socio-economic up-liftment and financial sustainability (M. Hudson et al 2020; J. Morduch, 1999) [14, 9]. But it is remarked that a large number of poor continue to remain outside the fold of the formal financial banking system, in spite of expansion of wide network of the organised banking system deep into rural areas (Sibghatallah Nasir, 2013) [26]. Studies from Bangladesh where the Yunus's Grameen Bank model is popular in along with Bolivia, Indonesia and India (B. Gutierrez Nieto et al. 2019) [4], reveals that increased household consumption, non-land assets, and improved education (Pitt & Khandker, 1998; S.R. Khandkar, 2005, Sharma and Zeller, 1997) [16, 22, 15].

Microfinance positively contributed to the overall growth in standard of living and livelihood activities (Madhubalaswamy, 2014) [17]. Microfinance is a catalyst of financial inclusion specifically in the developing regions (Soofia Fatima, 2024) [27]. It is a process which gives ability to make life choices in a context where this ability was denied early (Kabeer, 2002) [28]. MFIs are the effectors of household income by encouraging productivity, enhancing diversity of production and productivity and maximum use of existing available resources (Binswanger, 2007; Dejene, 2007; Sudan, 2007; Akintoye, 2008) [5, 7, 29, 1]. Participants in the microfinance activates enjoy the benefit of higher education and decrease in the vulnerability to economic shock and attain greater empowerment (Tessi Swope, 2005) [30] previous studies like Kabeer (2005) [12], Mayoux (2000) [18], Otero, M. (2019) [19], found that microfinance is a good strategy to eliminate economic development. The poor in the society has been considered as "high risk" and not served by the formal financial institutions. Further, women in the society are marginalised and faces difficult in accessing formal credit in account of lack of security (Laha and Kuri, 2014, Saramathi et al. 2011, Peprah, 2012) [13, 25, 20].

Statement of the problem

Income generating activities are important for women as they improve living standards, financial independence and overall wellbeing. They provide many opportunities to enhance income, build resources and attain personal goals. Engaging in IGAs can create a more stable financial portfolio. The generated income can be used to access essential services like education, healthcare, housing and improving the overall quality of life. In order to safeguard against digital divide poor women in the rural and urban requires sufficient resources and engaging in IGAs leads to avoid digital poor. Income generation can be a strong and powerful tool of poverty alleviation. SHGs are formed with the intention of attaining increased income through collective effort. The challenges like more self reliant, use of local resources and caring of community members can be successfully faced through earning more income. The selection of mix of IGAs depends on local context. Poor women of rural and urban face different challenges like lack of income opportunity, limited access to socio economic

service etc. can be navigated successfully with pooled resources. When income is an important dimension of livelihood systems, IGAs provide a key source of surviving and strengthening these systems. Microfinance is the best way to accessing borrowings, savings, investment and to fight against poverty and unemployment. The government recent welfare schemes which has been acting as a catalyst in empowering women. More awareness has to be created regarding savings and financial literacy.

Review of Literature

Soofia Fatima (2024) [27] research paper highlights on the concept of microfinance, MF's, and their outreach and their socio economic impact on the local population and fostering sustainable development. The study found that almost that MFIs have significantly expanded their outreach in Bihar particularly in rural areas. Microfinance has proved to be a game changer, providing social empowerment, financial inclusion and economic prosperity. Further the researcher expressed that microfinance may continue to be a key player in creating a more affluent and inclusive future for Bihar.

Sangeetha, G. (2023) [23] concentrated on the study of MFIs in promoting financial inclusion and driving economic development. The researcher used Exploratory Research Design to find the role of MFIs in promoting financial inclusion and economic development. Secondary data was used from published articles and journals. The main intention of the study is to know the impact of MFIs on financial inclusion, poverty reduction, and economic development. The finding of the study includes MFI's concentrating on the poor, deserved, disadvantaged population, financially underserved, women in rural areas. They offered a range of financial products and service tailored to the needs of the target population. MFIs adopted client centric approach and often use non-traditional methods to assess the credit worthiness of potential borrowers.

In recent work by Bryon et al. (2024) [31] run a novel experiment in Egypt where a large leader selected a sample of client firms that it believed might benefit from a larger loan: among this group, a control group had their own size doubled, whereas a treatment group had their loan size quadrupled. In comparing these groups the authors found mostly null average impact of larger loans but important heterogeneity in treatment effects, along with strong evidence of misallocation. The researchers only discover this heterogeneity by including a combination of clients psychometric and cognitive data and this suggest that psychometric data may be particularly important for leader seeking to identify high potential clients.

The research work by Andrea Gatto (2022) [2] aims to address the problem of financial inclusion and resilience in the current sustainable development framework. As per the researchers that the microfinance can play a decisive role in smoothing the risk of adverse events. It acts as resilience policy, tackling vulnerability and poverty, empowering people and vulnerable categories and enhancing their capabilities. The researchers use summate content analysis on the UN General Assembly Resolution, fulfilling a research gap. The study found increased importance attributed to the topic, key issues and policy strengths and limitations. The analysis reveals that the environmental

dimension is still neglected. The findings suggest investing in these channels, drafting governance pattern and modelling resilience and development policy to drive improved ecological and institution results.

Ejona Duci et al. (2025) [8] reveals that microfinance plays an important role in increasing financial inclusion through flexi credit opportunities, particularly for the low income people and small business. Researchers adopts a quantitative approach using survey method focusing on micro financial borrowers. Descriptive statistical method and graphical analysis was employed for the analysis of data. The study highlights the criticalness of microfinance in business growth and income stability. The findings reveal that a balanced proportion of borrowers reinvest in their business primarily for expansion, 37% and technological up-gradation 8% and asset buying 10%. More than 50% of respondents reported stable income despite fluctuations.

Objectives

1. To study the impact of demographics on IGAs, savings formation and investment and factors driving women sustainability.
2. To analyse the measuring effects of IGAs before and after joining SHGs.
3. To study the types of savings before and after joining SHGs.
4. To analyse the factors driving women sustainability.

Hypotheses

1. There is no greater variation in the demographics and hence do not impact on IGAs, saving formation and

- investment and factors driving women sustainability.
2. There is no difference between before and after effects on IGAs.
3. There exist no variations in savings before and after joining SHGs.
4. There are no factor driving women sustainability.

Research questions

1. What may be reasons behind the demographics not impact on IGAs, savings and drivers of women sustainability?
2. What is the measured affects of IGAs before and after joining SHGs?
3. What is the extent of savings and its investment before and after joining SHGs?
4. What are the factors that drives women sustainability?

Research Methodology

Data Source: The present study is based on both primary and secondary sources. Primary source gathered through a purposely developed interview schedule. Researcher gathered the primary data through interviewing the rural respondents of 6 villages. The secondary sources include NABARD and status of microfinance report, NRLM reports on groups and Karnataka State Official Website Panchatantra/Karnataka.gov.in.

Coverage of the study: The study covered selected villages of 6 blocks of Chikkaballapura district. These 6 blocks include. Chikkaballapura Kasaba, Gowribidanuru, Gudibande, Bagepalli, Sidlaghatta and Chintamani.

Sample and sampling fixation: Mode of sample fixation

Block Name	No. of SHGs	Total members	Sample Village	SHGs	Total members	Sample
Bagepalli	1587	15248	Gorthapalli	41	419	14
Chikkaballapur	1488	15234	Doddamarali	74	714	23
Chintamani	2072	21322	Enigadale	48	561	18
Gowribidanur	2123	21846	Alipura	24	238	7
Gudibande	487	4570	Varlakonda	68	590	19
Sidlaghatta	1574	15891	Chimangala	57	567	19
Total	9331	94111	6 Villages	312	3089	100

Source: (1) nrlm/nrlm/in?shg, (2) Ministry of Rural Development, (3) Sample based on members total in sample village, (4) Sample = Total members from 6 villages / members in sample villages x 100.

The sample of study fixed at 100. Sample is fixed based on the total number of members of selected village. Convenient sampling technique is followed in the conduct of interview which was conducted in a natural setting by visiting the respondents houses.

Line of analysis

The present study is a descriptive nature. Comparative modified ANOVA, Kendall's co-efficient of concordance, chi-square and contingency co-efficient quantitative technique were performed. To measure the extent of sustainability of women Extent of Sustainability Index was performed. Microsoft Excel 16 used to find variation in the data through ANOVA.

Participants: The participants of the study includes the residents of selected six villages from the six blocks of Chikkaballapura district. All the participants belongs to

rural areas urban Chikkaballapura, semi-urban areas, where agriculture and commercial crops are cultivated. Chikkaballapura is famous travelling centre and attracts people from different states. Most popular centres are Nandi Hills where the SAARC summit was held and another popular center is Isha Foundation.

Extent of sustainability Index (ESI): Based on 3 point Likert scale ESI was constructed. The weights are 3, 2, 1. The bipolar opinions of respondents is multiplied by the corresponding weights and the sum is totalled that decides the rank of particular statement.

Limitations

1. The study is confined to Chikkaballapura district.
2. The sample villages are only 6 block-wise.
3. The sample is 100 and any dependency on this research work requires further in depth study.

Survey Findings

Table 1 - Unbosom the data on demographic profile of respondents. To measure the impact effect, χ^2 and contingency co-efficient were performed. Table reveals that 84 respondents are married, 10 single and 6 divorces. 45 respondents belongs to the age group of 30-40 years, 17 to the 20 - 30 years, 25 > 50 years, 7 between 40-50 and 6 < 20 years. The education data reveals that 40 completed 10th standard, 20 degree, 16 pre high school, 13 ITI certificate holders, 5 PG Degree holders and 6 illiterates. Majority of i.e., 44 respondents are vegetable sellers, 20 seasonal fruit sellers, 13 each petty shop and agriculture and 10 pickle and papad sellers. Income data reveals that 52 respondents monthly earnings fall in between 10-20K, 25 to the 20-30K, 13 to the > 30K and 10 to the 5-10K. 45 are living in village, 20 urban Chikkaballapura district, 16 semi-urban, 10 remote villages, and 9 living in slums. 95 participates in social activities, 75 are trained, 15 not trained 10 are waiting. 10 contest in local elections and 90 support a candidate and voting. All the demographics are showing variation significantly with high degree of relationship.

Table 2 & 3 divulge data on measurement of effects of involvement in IGAs before and after joining SHGs. To measure the same comparative modified ANOVA has been performed. There are 73 respondents strongly agree over the statements and 16 agree and 11 somewhat agree. 18 respondents involved in harvesting of agricultural activities before joining and the some stood at 33 after joining SHGs. Involvement in IGAs objective is justified and there is greater awareness among the members. There is a decrease from 11 to 7 masala packing before and after. Tailoring is preferred even after joining SHGs and it was 16 before and 18 after joining. Respondents of Chikkaballapura district are familiar with involvement in harvesting commercial crops and hence more number are involved. F value before exhibits greater variation and whereas the same is decreased showing lesser variation. The P value before joining is $5.7E-05 < 0.05$ and hence null hypotheses that there is no greater

variation is rejected. Further, the F value after joining is 8.65 and P-value is $0.002327 < 0.05$ and similarity the H_0 is rejected and hence it is concluded that there exist greater variation in the data.

Table 4 and 5 disclose data on the types of savings before and after joining SHGs. Table discloses that 24 respondents parked their savings with chit funds followed by 22 with relatives / friends/ neighbours. 7 respondents hold cash in hand and 9 kept their savings with banks. The situation after joining show a different situation and this change emerged only due to enhanced level of awareness. Savings invested with chit funds only 3, and with relatives / friends/ neighbours 3, nearly 65% of the respondents i.e., 53 respondents invested only the SHGs which is a clear effect arised out of increase in the level of awareness. To a greater extent investment with relatives / friends / neighbours has been reduced. The "w" value before was 2.37 and after it stood at 6.153. The difference between the two is $6.153 - 2.37 = 3.783$ and the calculated value is being 79.443 being higher than the critical TV 14.067 and hence it is concluded that there exist significant relationship between before and after joining SHGs and data farther reveals that the respondents are more aware to invest their savings in a services way.

Table - 6 bring to light the driving factors of women sustainability. To measure the factors extent of driving women sustainability extent of sustainability Index (ESI) was performed. The bipolar opinions of respondents were multiplied by corresponding weights. Further to measure the significant variation χ^2 and contingency coefficient tests were conducted and finally result of contingency coefficient was obtained. Ranking of statements was done on the basis of ESI. The first rank was awarded to development of financial skills and quality of leadership the second rank was awarded to cooperation between the marketers and the third rank was given to using loan for productive purpose. The remaining factors were ranked depending upon the strength of ESI.

Table 1: Demographic profile of Respondents

Demographics	χ^2	TV @ 0.05	df	Result of χ^2	"c"	Result of c
Marital status	115.77	5.991	2	Significant	0.73	High Degree
Age (in years)	51.20	9.488	4	Significant	0.58	High Degree
Education	49.12	11.070	5	Significant	0.57	High Degree
Occupation	38.70	9.488	4	Significant	0.52	High Degree
Income (INR)	43.92	7.815	3	Significant	0.55	High Degree
Living conditions	39.48	9.488	4	Significant	0.53	High Degree
Participation in social activities	81.00	3.841	1	Significant	0.67	High Degree
Training	78.50	5.991	2	Significant	0.66	High Degree
Voting & supporting a candidate	64.00	3.841	1	Significant	0.62	High Degree

Source: Field Survey

Note: χ^2 = Chi-square

'c' = $\sqrt{(\chi^2 / \chi^2 + N)}$

Where 'c' = Contingency Co-efficient, N = Number of Observations

When the value 'c' is equal or nearer to 1, it means that there is high degree of association between attributes. Contingency co-efficient will always to be less than 1. High degree is considered here if 'c' is 0.50 and above.

Table 2: Measuring effects of involvement in IGAs Before Joining SHGs

		SA	A	SWA	T
1.	Running Petty shop	6	2	1	9
2.	Masala Packing	11	2	2	15
3.	Grocery shop with delivery service	8	2	1	11
4.	Working in harvesting of commercial crops	18	6	4	28
5.	Working as labour in APMC	9	1	-	10
6.	Tailoring	16	2	1	19
7.	Working in Readymade Garment Units	5	1	2	8
	Total	73	16	11	100

Source: Field Survey

Summary: Single Factor ANOVA

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Column 1	7	73	10.42857	24.28571
Column 2	7	16	2.285714	2.94762
Column 3	7	11	1.571429	1.619048

Source: Field Survey

ANOVA

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-Value	F-Crit
Between groups	338.9524	2	169.4762	17.64793	5.72E-05	3.554557
Within groups	172.8095	18	9.603175			
Total	511.8095	20				

Source: Field Survey

ANOVA Analysis: To measure the IGAs status of respondents before joining SHGs a null hypotheses that there exist no significant variation in data was framed. The F-value and P-values are 17.64793 and 5.72E05 @ 5% level of significance with $V_1 = 2, V_2 = 18$.

Table 3: Measuring effects of involvement in IGAs After Joining SHGs

		SA	A	SWA	T
1.	Running Petty shop	8	2	-	10
2.	Masala Packing	7	1	-	8
3.	Grocery shop with delivery service	9	2	-	11
4.	Working in harvesting of commercial crops	33	2	1	36
5.	Working as labour in APMC	7	-	1	8
6.	Tailoring	18	2	1	21
7.	Working in Readymade Garment Units	4	1	1	06
	Total	86	10	4	100

Source: Field Survey

Summary: Single Factor ANOVA

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Column 1	7	86	12.28571	102.5714
Column 2	7	10	1.428571	0.619048
Column 3	7	1	0.5714529	0.281714

ANOVA

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-Value	F-Crit
Between groups	596.8524	2	298.4762	8.653474	0.002327	3.554557
Within groups	620.8571	18	34.49206			
Total	1217.81					

Source: Field Survey

ANOVA Analysis: For the comparison before and after effect both the F-value and the P-value are considered since they works together to decide statistical significance. F-value compares the variance between groups to the variance within groups and p-value decides the probability of observing such an F-value. Before joining F-value is 17.64793 and P-value 5.72E-05 and since the p-value is within the threshold value and hence H_0 is rejected. The P-value after joining stood at 8.653474 showing lower variation when compare to before effect and P-value being 0.002327 less than accepted level 0.05 and hence there exist greater variation in the IGAs of respondents in between before and after and respondents exhibit more awareness in selecting a particular type of IGA. The difference between P-value after and before is $0.002327 - 0.0000572 = 0.0022$ less than significance level 0.05 and hence there exist significant variation in the data and respondents are benefitted very much after joining SHGs.

Table 4: Types of savings before joining SHGs

Types of savings	SA	A	SWA	RT	RT ²
Provident Fund	2	2	1	5	25
SHGs	0	0	0	0	0
Cash in hand	7	2	1	10	100
Cash at Bank	9	3	1	13	169
Chit Fund	24	6	1	31	961
Post office	8	2	-	10	100
Relatives / Friends / Neighbours	22	4	2	28	784
Mutual funds	2	1	-	3	9
Total	74	20	6	100	2148

Source: Field Survey

Note: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, SWA = Somewhat Agree, RT = Row Total

$$SSR = \sum RT^2 - (\sum RT)^2 / N = 2148 - (100)^2 / 8 = 2148 - 1250 = 898$$

Use the sum of squares (SSR) in the following formula to obtain Kendall's W.

$$W = 12 \times SSR / k^2 N (N^2 - 1)$$

$$= 12 \times 898 / 9 \times 8 (64 - 1) = 10776 / 4536 = 2.37$$

Table 5: Types of savings after joining SHGs

Types of savings after joining	SA	A	SWA	RT	RT ²
Provident Fund	2	1	1	4	16
SHGs	53	1	3	57	32.49
Cash in hand	4	1	1	6	36
Cash at Bank	10	2	1	13	169
Chit Fund	3	1	1	5	25
Post office	4	1	1	6	36
Relatives / Friends / Neighbours	3	2	1	6	36
Mutual funds	2	1	-	3	9
Total	81	10	9	100	3576

Source: Field Survey

Note: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, SWA = Somewhat Agree, RT = Row Total

$$SSR = \sum RT^2 - (\sum RT)^2 / N$$

$$= 3576 - (100)^2 / 8 = 3576 - 1250 = 2326$$

Use the sum of squares (SSR) in the following formula to obtain Kendall's W.

$$W = 12 \times SSR / k^2 N (N^2 - 1)$$

$$= 12 \times 2326 / 9 \times 8 (64 - 1) = 27912 / 4536 = 6.153$$

Now find the difference between 6.153 - 2.37 = 3.783

Test the significance of "w" by using the chi-square statistic.

$$\chi^2 = k (n - 1) w = 3 (8 - 1) 3.783 = 79.443$$

Decision: At 7 df (8-1) with 0.05 level of significance the TV = 14.067. The calculated value being 79.434 being higher than the critical TV and hence "w" fails to accept H₀ and accepts H₁. Therefore, it is concluded that there exist significant variation in the data and with high degree of relationship between before and after SHGs and respondents are very much interested and where to park their savings after joining SHGs.

Table 6: Factors driving women sustainability

Factors driving sustainability of members	Extent of sustainability			ESI	R	x ²	Result of x ²	"c"	Result of C
	SA	A	SWA						
Cooperation between the members	81	14	5	276	II	103.38	Significant	0.70	High Degree
	243	28	5						
Frequency of attending meetings	60	21	19	241	XV	32.06	Significant	0.50	High Degree
	180	42	19						
Rotation of own savings	61	22	17	244	XIV	34.82	Significant	0.51	High Degree
	183	44	17						
Graduation towards micro enterprise development	66	16	18	248	XIII	48.08	Significant	0.56	High Degree
	198	32	18						
Providing organisational and financial support	65	20	15	250	XII	45.50	Significant	0.55	High Degree
	195	40	15						
Using loan for productive purpose	74	19	7	267	III	76.58	Significant	0.65	High Degree
	222	38	7						
Government procedures	69	16	15	254	X	57.26	Significant	0.60	High Degree
	207	32	15						
Development of financial skills and quality of leadership	89	9	2	287	I	140.19	Significant	0.76	High Degree
	267	18	2						
Average loan balance per borrower	74	17	9	265	IV	75.8	Significant	0.66	High Degree

	222	34	9						
Yield on group loan portfolio	67	23	10	257	IX	53.54	Significant	0.59	High Degree
	201	46	10						
Training	63	27	10	253	XI	43.94	Significant	0.55	High Degree
	189	54	10						
Retain from SHGs	73	12	15	258	VII	70.94	Significant	0.55	High Degree
	219	24	15						
Repayment of loan	74	16	10	264	V	74.96	Significant	0.63	High Degree
	222	32	10						
Monitoring loan utilisation	72	14	14	258	VII	67.28	Significant	0.63	High Degree
	216	28	14						
Insist on more awareness among members	72	16	12	260	VI	67.13	Significant	0.63	High Degree
	216	32	12						

Source: Field Survey.

Note: TV = 5.991

$\chi^2 = \text{Chi-square}$; 'c' = $\sqrt{(x^2 / x^2 + N)}$

Where 'c' = Contingency Co-efficient, N = Number of Observations

When the value 'c' is equal or nearer to 1, it means that there is high degree of association between attributes. Contingency co-efficient will always be less than 1. High degree is considered here if 'c' is 0.50 and above.

df = n-1 = 2, TV = 5.991, df = n-1 = 2

ESI = Extent of sustainability Index

Discussion

The emergence of microfinance can be traced to the failure of financial institutions in providing financial assistance to the poor, depressed and uncared persons. Innovations like group lending, joint liability, frequent repayments etc. have reshaped the practices of micro finance. More aware respondents earn by indulging in better income generating activities. Respondents working in agriculture land, retail trade of cut fruits, working in APMC yard etc., have shown better income than the others. The study found that all the demographics of respondents are well supporting the involvement by IGAs and savings formation. Women respondents are more aware of the factors driving women sustainability. After joining SHGs respondents in one number in the area of harvesting commercial crops. Further, a marginal increase in the number of tailor also found. Study also found increase in the petty shop owners. As per as savings investments are concerned, a remarkable change is found in the chit funds investments. After joining SHGs, one can find a dramatic change and now the respondents interest is to move to other form of secured investment schemes. Majority of the respondents invested in SHGs and curbed the practice of investing with friends / relation and neighbours. The study found factors like development of financial skills and quality of leadership, cooperation between the members and using loan for productive purpose in the owner drives women sustainability. The data collected is well presented in the form of tables and appropriate quantitative techniques are performed to measure the variability and degree of relationship. Extent of sustainability index technique appropriately performed to know the rank of factors driving women sustainability.

Conclusion

MFI's should come out with a clear policy regarding outstanding loan collection. SHGs should lend money and should monitor the loan utilisation. They should see that the sanctioned loan should be used only towards productive purpose. The poor now better than the previous and can save due to the Karnataka State Governments implementation of 5 welfare schemes. The study found that all the demographics supporting the study. The effects of

involvement in IGAs found better among the respondents who have joined SHGs. More number of respondents involved in the economic activity of harvesting commercial crops and tailoring. Respondents have stopped parking their savings with chit funds and friends / relatives / neighbourhood and instead invest in SHGs which is one of the change emerged on account of enhanced awareness. Further, the study found that factors like development of financial skills and quality of leadership, cooperation between the members and using loan for productive purpose.

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